

A hi-tec Business Unit dynamic simulator

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Abstract

A dynamic business unit simulator is presented as a stand-alone personal computer application. The simulator uses a standard office-type worksheet for input and output data, while the calculation algorithm is implemented with routines of embedded software programs. The practical implementation of the simulator is based on a real model of a start-up company in the hi-tech sector. The simulator allows the input of business and structural data related to the operation of the unit, data that can in turn be recursively modified and adapted during simulation sessions. The output of the tool covers both physical and financial quantities, making possible what-if analysis with respect to market and/or structural changes in the business unit. Projections of workloads and external resources needed to achieve budget goals are also generated. The simulator can be used as a tool to analyze, compare, refine and validate issues from the study of the real business unit processes and relevant data mining.

1. Introduction

The current availability of powerful Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems enables the planning and control of the production cycle of modern Business Units (BUs). These ERP systems are usually largely integrated into the BU "life cycle" and are implemented as complex, proprietary or commercial software systems installed on cloud or dedicated local servers. These tools also enable the preparation of the BU's annual Budget and Business Plan. These documents become fixed targets to be pursued to achieve the industrial goals of the company or business unit. However, very often it is useful for BU managers or investors to make quick forecasts about the effects of changes in BU activity (including also processes and organization) and/or market scenario. Therefore, an agile, self-contained IT application, as representative as possible of the BU's "life cycle", can help in this regard. This paper outlines the approach followed to build a simulation tool capable of running on a standard notebook with a real BU used as a case study. This simulator conforms to the BU Budget/Plan and is able to simulate changes in business plan inputs or changes in the BU's internal production parameters in real time. These changes lead to detailed results for both production volumes and financial magnitudes. The simulator application is run -via developed macro software routines- on a standard PC using a commercial spreadsheet application.

2. The sequential machine

In the following Fig. 1, a general scheme of the simulator is given. It appears like a general sequential machine where some inputs are transformed, after a Δt processing time, into deterministic outputs, when an internal structure of the machine \mathbf{X} is defined and fixed. In our BU case, the independent input variable is the C_{qv} symbol, meaning a "C" customer contract order with "q" quantity and "v" economic value (or product price). The simulated outputs are "physical" products, with their technical features, expressed by the P_{qv} magnitude and "economical" issues in terms of values (costs, revenues, margins, cash etc.) expressed by the output E_{qv} . An additional M_{qv} input magnitude is needed, as dependent variable, in the form of external resources (e.g. materials & services) needed for the achievement of the C_{qv} customer order. Finally, the internal actual BU structure is addressed by the "vector" \mathbf{X} that includes various features of the BU: organization, work force, equipment, etc. In the event of unexpected or unsatisfactory results, corrective actions can be made as changes to the \mathbf{X} structure or product characteristics. These changes will result in "feedback" to the BU's market presence and competitiveness.

Fig. 1 The BU simulator sequential machine scheme

In Fig. 2 the formal relations between the above said magnitudes are presented. From the equation (4) in particular it is seen that the economic issues of the BU can be affected by changes in profitability and/or "volume" of contracts. The simulation of these output variations vs C_{qv} and X parameters, is precisely the aim of the simulator implementation.

$$P_{qv} = f(X, C_{qv}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{qv} = g(X, C_{qv}) \quad (2)$$

$$dP_{qv} = \frac{\partial f(X, C_{qv})}{\partial X} dX + \frac{\partial f(X, C_{qv})}{\partial C_{qv}} dC_{qv} \quad (3)$$

$$dE_{qv} = \frac{\partial g(X, C_{qv})}{\partial X} dX + \frac{\partial g(X, C_{qv})}{\partial C_{qv}} dC_{qv} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 2 Formal relations between input/output magnitudes

3. The target Business Unit

The target Business Unit to be simulated was a real hi-tec company acting at start-up level in the aerospace market. The activity of this BU is performed by means of contracts with customers covering the development of advanced on-board systems using mechanical and electronic technologies with embedded flight software. These innovative products basically include also not recurring design activities. These contracts are completed usually in several months or pluriannual time, depending on complexity and innovation of the products. The production cycle therefore must cover: contracts acquisition, procurement of external resources as appropriate, development, manufacturing, testing, qualification and delivery of the final products, with high quality standards during of the overall cycle to be guaranteed. The economic return of the BU activity is therefore the result of many concurring contracts managed as internal work programs generating both costs and revenues. The BU cash flow is obtained with payments at contractual milestones completion. The simulator must therefore be as much as possible compliant with these business objects and features and with the internal processes of the BU. In the following figures some simplified sketches of the above said processes are given. From these figures it is clear that the involved magnitudes can vary with type and time. These variations must be handled by the simulator. Figures 3 and 4 show that the business development process covers different professional specializations (disciplines), while the procurement of external resources includes various types of goods, including hi-rel. components, to be merged in the production process. Therefore, processing steps must be coordinated with each other and with the process of procuring external resources. During product completion, labor and external resource costs (materials etc.) are then expended, and in parallel an added value is then created as the work progresses (Fig. 5). This leads to realizing economic margins, for each specific contract, which is the company's business goal. An organization capable of handle these processes work is thus necessary. In the following we will present a description of the case study based on Pro Forma data. These data are realistic and mutually consistent but are used only to test the simulator and in no way represent any consolidated BU reporting data. We will also hide specific references to acronyms and codes that refer to the actual BU and are of no interest to the reader.

Fig. 3 Different work force disciplines/activities quantity distribution along contract program implementation phases

Fig. 4 Different external resources average need along contract program implementation time

Fig. 5 A simplified graph of cumulative Costs/Revenues along the contract program implementation time

3.1 The BU organization

The Fig. 6 shows the organization of the BU under study. The basic pattern is that of a structure divided into direct and indirect (staff) working sections, respectively. The direct sections are directly involved in the customer contract implementation and are divided according to the specific professional skills required by the BU's production process (Fig. 7). The indirect sections are related to general & administration, human resources management, marketing and commercial effort and ICT. The use of external resources also requires a procurement internal structure. For these process characteristics, the BU must have a system for managing the individual contract through a program manager using planning and reporting tools. Product and process quality will be ensured by a Product Assurance system also organized with managers in charge of.

Fig. 6 The organization of the BU under study

Program Management
Subco Purchase
Production
Manufacturing
Testing
System Engineering
Mechanical and thermal Engi
Propulsion Engineering
Hardware Engineering
Software Engineering
ACS Engineering
Tribology Engineering
Production Engineering
PA
Quality Control
Safety

Machinery and equipment
Raw materials
Stationery/writing materials
Stock picking
Consultants
Third-party services
Standars Outsourced Work
Equipment's maintenance and repair
Insurances
Travels
Personnel's other costs
Personnel's training
Other costs

Fig. 7 The direct work sections and the types of external resources

3.2 The Products / Programs resource data

In addition to an ERP internal system (not discussed in the present work) the BU will use a computer aided planning for the Contracts/Products/Programs implementation. In other terms, each work program will be associated to a planned network of activities (GANTT or PERT like). Ref. [1]. For our work we will use the summary data outputs of those networks in terms of monthly distribution of the resources. We call this data set the Product Resource Data Sheet, that -for each standard product or activity- collects expected work time hours and materials costs. Fig. 8 depicts the scheme for a typical product non-recurring development example while Fig. 9 shows a similar data sheet for a recurrent product example.

ITEM DESCR.		STANDARD PRODUCT RESOURCE DATA SHEET																						
MONTHS		GRAND TOTALS																						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20			
TOTAL HOURS/MONTH		63708	3046	3046	3366	3686	5072	5212	4912	4392	3952	3792	3296	3264	2664	2664	2664	2664	2664	1580	1580			
TOTAL MAT. & SERV. /MONTH		40517	18933	8333	35625	28375	17292	14292	12192	38042	136792	48792	6000	26750	150000	0	0	0	25000	0	0			
RESOURCES DETAIL		RESOURCE CODE	Description	Type	Abbr																			
DIRECT HOURS						70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70		
			Program Management	T																				
			Subco Purchase	T																				
			Production	T																				
			Manufacturing	T					320					240	240									
			Testing	T																				
			System Engineering	T		810	810	585	585	905	746	746	746	746	585	435	435	544	544	544	544	320	320	
			Mechanical and the	T		160	160	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	
			Propulsion Engineer	T		384	384	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	
			Hardware Engineer	T		224	224	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	960	
			Software Engineer	T		420	420	560	560	880	392	392	392	392	1600	960	720	2380	2380	1820	1820	1820	1820	
			ACS Engineering	T		704	704	320	320	746	746	746	746	746	746	746	746	140	140	160	160	160	160	
			Tribology Engineer	T		224	224	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	
			Production Engineer	T																				
			PA	T		70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	
			Quality Control	T																				
			Safety	T																				
DIRECT CDSTS(E)		AA	Machinery and equipment	AA																				
		AM	Raw materials	AM																				
		AC	Stationery/writing materials	AC																				
		PM	Stock picking (prelevi da magazzino)	PM		0	0	0	0	30000	3000	0	0	25000	125000	40000	0	0	15000					
		CO	Consultants	CO		8333	8333	28125	8125	9792	8792	8792	8792	8792	8792	8792	8792	4000	4000	0	15000			
		PT	Third-party services	PT																				
		LE	Standards Outsourced Work	LE		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20000	0				
		MR	Equipment's maintenance and repair	MR																				
		AS	Insurances	AS																				
		VT	Travels	VT		10600	0	7500	250	2500	500	2500	4250	3000	0	2000	2750	0						
		AP	Personnel's other costs	AP																				
		FP	Personnel's training	FP																				
		CD	Other costs	CD																				

Fig. 8 Direct hours and external resources monthly needed for a non-recurring product development example

In the case depicted in Fig.8 we have an implementation time of 19 months with a work load of about 64000 hours total, involving mainly design and "breadboard" testing. In the case depicted in Fig. 9 we have an implementation time of 18 months total with a work load of about 26000 hours and about 3 million Euro external costs, these last mainly due to hi-rel. qualified electronic and mechanical components.

ITEM DESCR.		STANDARD PRODUCT RESOURCE DATA SHEET																			2017				
MONTHS		GRAND TOTALS																							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19					
TOTAL HOURS/MONTH		25940	1166,667	806,6667	806,6667	1093,333	1013,333	1013,333	1093,333	1093,333	1093,333	3260	3260	2000	1200	1200	1680	1386,667	1386,667	1386,667	0				
TOTAL MAT. & SERV. /MONTH		2962000	2000	3000	2000	0	6000	0	2000	4000	146000	1556000	2000	16000	32000	30000	1125000	16000	10000	10000	0				
RESOURCES DETAIL		RESOURCE CODE	Description	Type	Abbr																				
DIRECT HOURS						80	80	80	80	80	80	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	80	80	80				
			Program Management	T																					
			Subco Purchase	T																					
			Production	T																					
			Manufacturing	T		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	573	573	107	53	53	160	53	53			
			Testing	T		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	413	413	160	107	107	80	107	107			
			System Engineering	T		207	127	127	213	133	133	133	133	133	107	107	427	320	320	320	213	213			
			Mechanical and the	T		86	86	86	0	0	0	0	0	0	147	147	160	53	53	160	53	53			
			Propulsion Engineer	T		288	120	120	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	207	133	27	27	160	27	27			
			Hardware Engineer	T		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	640	640	107	107	107	0	213	213			
			Software Engineer	T		53	53	53	267	267	267	267	267	267	320	320	107	107	107	0	213	213			
			ACS Engineering	T		288	200	200	80	80	80	80	80	80	213	213	213	0	0	320	320	320			
			Tribology Engineer	T		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	147	147	107	0	0	160	0	0			
			Production Engineer	T		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
			PA	T		80	80	80	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160			
			Quality Control	T		107	67	67	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	213	160	107	107	320	107	107			
			Safety	T																					
DIRECT CDSTS(E)		AA	Machinery and equipment	AA																					
		AM	Raw materials	AM																					
		AC	Stationery/writing materials	AC																					
		PM	Stock picking (prelevi da magazzino)	PM		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1440000	0	0	0	1075000	0	0		
		CO	Consultants	CO		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		PT	Third-party services	PT		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30000	30000	40000	0	10000		
		LE	Standards Outsourced Work	LE		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	120000	110000	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		MR	Equipment's maintenance and repair	MR																					
		AS	Insurances	AS																					
		VT	Travels	VT		2000	3000	2000	0	6000	0	2000	4000	26000	0	2000	16000	2000	0	10000	16000	0			
		AP	Personnel's other costs	AP																					
		FP	Personnel's training	FP																					
		CD	Other costs	CD																					

Fig. 9 Direct hours and external resources monthly needed for a recurring product development example

3.3 The BU economic figures to be simulated

3.3.1 The hourly cost rate

One of the simulator tasks is the forecasting of the BU economic performance vs different market inputs or internal structure variation. These economical magnitudes come from the execution of Programs/Contracts carried out by the company according to orders received by costumers. As before seen, these programs involve resources like manpower and materials & services to fulfill the required outputs of program milestones. The combined mix of milestones value and resources costs leads to an economical result (cash, margin & profit) for the company that must be assessed in terms of accounting figures and issues. For this task the method of direct costing has been followed, Ref. [2-3], leading to an hourly cost rate (HCR) for the direct work hours, to be used for margin computation. This HCR is computed for each direct structure (defined as Cost Center) of the BU. Next Fig. 10 shows the scheme by a generic section example. The basic idea is to associate to the direct work hour some costs not only related to people salaries but also to some other cost "quotas" that can be reasonably associated for the contract completion, thus leading to a "transformation" cost figure.

GENERIC COST CENTER HOUR RATE COMPUTATION (absolutely arbitrary data)							
NUMBER OF PEOPLE	LABOUR COST	CC COSTS	AMORTIZ. COSTS	QUOTA DISTR. CC	TOTAL CC COSTS	HOURS DEVELOPED	HOUR RATE PARAMETER
8	€ 400.000,00	€ 35.000,00	€ 12.500,00	€ 19.600,00	€ 467.100,00	€ 13.440	€ 34,75

Fig.10 Hourly Cost Rate parameter definition for a generic direct structure (Cost Centre-CC)

In the above figure (based on arbitrary data considered for a hypothetical year budget) the main transformation cost components are computed as follows:

- Labour Cost: total labour cost coming from gross salaries of the people present in the CC
- CC Cost: fixed costs (materials & services) due to specific direct CC operation
- Amortization Costs: computed as the amortization quota of specific investments of the CC
- Distributable CC Quota: quota of total company distributable CC (e.g. energy, building rental costs, etc) apportioned over the number of people heads
- Total CC Costs: the sum of above items
- Hours Developed: the year budget direct hours capability of the CC people team
- H. Rate Parameter: Total CC Costs divided by the Hours Developed

3.3.2 Company Economic Magnitudes vs Direct Costing

The fulfilling of the various acquired programs/contracts concurrent along the BU fiscal year, leads to overall economical magnitudes. Fig. 11 shows the main economic magnitudes for a typical annual business exercise. In this figure we assume for the sake of simplicity a yearly business activity of the company, having achieved and concluded a single order contract, whose value is VCTR (yellow left bar). To complete the contract, a certain quantity of external resources has been used, giving rise to relevant costs called MAT (brown bar). Comparing VCTR with MAT we obtain the so-called added value (VA). This VA is in turn composed by other important economic magnitudes: labor cost (CL), yearly amortization (AMM), fixed costs of operation of cost centers (CC) and –finally- the resultant profit figure. Now, part of the CL+AMM+CC total figure will be directly applied to program completion (transformation + mat. handling costs), while the residual part will be spent to cover company staff operations costs and R&D expenses. The H rectangle indicates the direct hours component present in the labor cost and transformation costs. The gross margin achieved will be used to cover the staff cost and the final annual profit (here before interest & taxes). Note that the gross margin will include also a research & development cost annual quota expended by the BU. In this scheme the COGS (Costs of Good Sold) are made up by transformation costs plus the external materials & services. In case of pluriannual timespan of the contracts, the calculation of the production value at a given intermediate time before contract completion is computed with the "cost-to-cost" method. Under this method, the advancement of production value over total contract value is calculated in the same proportion as the advancement of contract program costs over its total costs. Ref [4]. The Simulator will manage these quantities and methods providing the relevant outputs vs what-if tests.

Figure 11 - Main economic magnitudes for one year operation

3.3.3 BU Budget & Plan

The Fig. 11 economic magnitudes are involved in the BU Budget and in the five years pluriannual Plan. The BU's Budget / Plan scheme starts with a commercial plan to acquire orders and contracts from customers identified as potential buyers. Based on this commercial plan, internal development/production programs are defined generating requirements for workloads, materials & services and the needed equipment to be made available for the budget programs completion. The necessary investments consistent with the production goals are also defined. To realize these goals, a plan for staffing and material purchases is then defined. Marketing plans and new market penetration are also included. Operations fixed costs for the given BU structure and periodic maintenance are also included in the Budget/Plan. Finally, financial targets consistent with production targets are made explicit in dedicated balance reports (Profit & Loss, Balance, Cash Flow sheets). The preparation and presentation of the BU Budget / Plan is out of scope of the present work. The study case BU Budget / Plan structure is however used -supplied with Pro Forma data- to test the simulator tool. For this purpose, the Budget/Plan is presented in the form of a worksheet file that includes many spreadsheets. All the data will cover five fiscal years (FY1 to FY5) of Plan at monthly detail (60 months timespan) plus an initial Fiscal Year Zero (FY0).

4. The BU simulator

The simulator is integrated with the Budget / Plan worksheet through macro software procedures embedded in the system. These macro routines are developed using the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) available in the worksheet application. Fig. 12 shows a typical simulator IDE window. It is here seen that the Budget/Plan spreadsheets for our study are 27 in number and are processed with nine software modules. The software modules are written using a modern object-oriented BASIC coding language. Ref [5-6].

Fig. 12 The simulator IDE software development window

The simulation session then starts assuming an initial condition of the BU: the X condition introduced in section 2.0. This is the initial structure of the BU, based on a given number of people heads, equipment, facilities and operating costs, all according to the Budget/Plan approved for the BU. This business structure is then fed by processing a specific input commercial plan (CP), i.e. a number of contracts/programs to be fulfilled along a defined timescale (each contract with a specific kick off time and duration). With these initial conditions the simulator analyzes dynamically the input data and provides the expected outputs both in terms of workloads & resources to be met and financial results along the 60 months of the plan. The user of the simulator, after evaluating the first run output, can decide to change the inputs (CP or X data) and rerun another iteration session to see the effects of the variations imposed (what-if analysis). The flow-chart of the process is given in the following Fig. 13.

Fig. 13 The simulator iterative process flow-chart

The simulator user interface ("main" window) appears as per the following Fig. 14.

Fig. 14 The simulator main command computer interface

From the "main" window, a number of software macros can be activated via available buttons (rectangularly or oval shaped on "main" front end). These macro-buttons use, as input/output data, a number of support sheets available in the worksheet. As appropriate during the simulation session, there are highlighted areas in the sheets presented to the user where the user can change the input data, thus allowing for a new simulation with new data. The results of computations coming from input data, are presented in dedicated output views that in turn can be recalled through dedicated macro-buttons. The sheet "CP" is a detailed description of sales opportunities that can be changed in number and time position (input data) as in Fig 15. Pushing the button "Sum of the items sold" the system generates a sum up of products (Commercial Plan Summary Sales - BCP) for a quick testing of business scenario. In both CP or BCP tables the user can change the input data to rerun the simulation test. These possible changes involve the number or type of the item sold and also the expected contract values. In "BCP" standard prices and products cost sheets are assumed, while in "CP" sheet dedicated prices can be specified. The standard costs (hours & mat.) associated to the products can be also modulated by multiplying coefficients (defined at the ends of the CP / BCP rows) vs commonality or complexity of the specific contract. Clicking over the central oval figures, the new commercial inputs from "BCP" (or from "CP") are loaded and processed. The results are summarized in the dashboard view (pushing the dedicated button) as per Fig. 16 where different product types (P1-P7) are considered. A profit/loss (p/l) account can be also recalled via the dedicated pushbutton from "main" sheet. This p/l account is structured for quick look management analysis and ends at ebit level (Fig. 17). The revenues figures are computed as the value of the production. The total backlog and invoices figures are also presented in the dashboard, Fig. 16, and are based on the milestones pay plan covering four tranches of 25% each of the order contract value. These milestones are assumed equally spaced in time starting from the advance milestone at kickoff and ending with the last milestone at the final product delivery. The investment plan is also presented and generates an amortization schedule that is captured by the simulator. The balance sheets are also available via the suitable button and collect the standard balance statements including financial p/l, taxes, assets and cash figures. The basic compositions of manpower, skills material & services required are also available. Figures 18 and 19 show the detailed monthly profile for the overall required workloads and external resources. In Fig. 20 it is seen that a possible issue arises when the total direct workload requested by the input plan is higher than the available direct manpower. In this case the simulator automatically allocates the "delta" manpower to external outsourcing facilities considering however the relevant equivalent cost in the p/l reports (see Fig. 17 at line "External Works Costs. Moreover, a fraction of the available direct hours can be devoted to research and development for new products. This amount is varied by the user as input data and is highlighted as output in the p/l report in Fig. 17 at the "Strategic R&D" line.

Fig. 18 Required workforce (people number total & sections) by commercial plan inputs

Fig. 19 Required external resources (total & type) by commercial plan inputs (Hi-Rel parts main cost figure)

Fig. 20 Total required workload (people number) vs available budget direct manpower (dashed line) along 60 months timespan

5. Conclusion and comments

The simulator makes it possible to analyze and modify quantities such as price, cost, and time to make and sell products; costs can be evaluated based on their composition as both labor and external resources. Input contracts in the business plan are dynamically reallocated from the kick-off time, and resource loads and cash flows are recalculated accordingly. The BU structure can also be changed to study the effects of changes. Changes in model structure can relate to operating costs, capital expenditures, and related depreciation. Workloads are also elements addressed by the simulator, which provides the labor demand generated by the business plan and the labor potential due to the company's workforce. Differences between these workload demands and offers can be handled either as outsourcing or as changes in internal research hours. Finally, all standard financial and even management reports are generated as output from the simulator. All data are generated in monthly resolution and can be summarized on an annual basis in reports. The simulator thus created can be easily portable as it runs within a popular office application. It is contained in a single worksheet file along with dedicated software and performs the run of the study case simulation in about 12 seconds when used on a standard laptop with 4 GB Ram memory and Core i5 processor. The simulator operates on the basis of general principles of resource planning and economic evaluation, but nevertheless -because it operates in close integration with the corporate budget structure- it must be adapted to the processes/production reality of the individual company. The architecture of the simulation software, however, can be easily tailored and interfaced to the actual needs of any individual business unit, once defined and specified in the budget/plan. The analyses available as simulator outputs can be used by company management to explore various business options and various technical solutions for the implementation of the company's products. Sensitivity analysis and optimization exercises can also be performed with the tool thus available. The simulator automatically operates in an "open loop" once the inputs are defined. Iterations and retroactions with variable inputs must be performed interactively with the user, given the complexity and number of variables involved. Future developments may consider partially closing the loop by defining a target output and imposing automatic feedback rules (e.g. AI rules) to achieve the desired goal. The tool can also be used in connection with process optimization and data mining comparing simulated data results with actual data coming from the BU under analysis.

6. Acknowledgements

Special thanks to the BU management and Planning and Control section people for making available the Budget/Plan templates.

7. References

Author Note on References:

The literature on systems simulation and process analysis is enormous. It is beyond the scope and capacity of this article to attempt to review and make reference with these studies. We will therefore only refer to works strictly instrumental to the contents of this work, leaving the correlation with other studies on the topic to the interest and experience of the reader.

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